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BIOFIN-EU

PROTECTING AND RESTORING BIODIVERSITY USING MAINSTREAM FINANCE

D7.1: Dissemination, exploitation, communication plan M3

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Executive Summary

BIOFIN-EU seeks to create a unifying framework and technology that creates the enabling conditions for nature-positive investments. Activities that protect and restore biodiversity (such as nature-based solutions) are frequently unique and mainly carried out via multi-actor efforts at a local scale with positive, but complex outcomes. BIOFIN-EU will use a multi-actor approach to create impact through a science-led Dashboard which will help actors navigate large-scale financing challenges and to develop, replicate, scale out and strengthen NBS-investment, creating a more sustainable, vibrant, resilient and healthy planet and supporting the EU's biodiversity restoration ambitions. BIOFIN-EU will also produce several key exploitable results (KERs) that will offer extensive positive impact including:

- **NBS Database**
- **Nature-Positive Business Model Builder**
- **Data Analytics & Underwriting Engine**
- **Skills and Knowledge Accelerators**

The BIOFIN-EU deliverable D7.1 Dissemination, exploitation, communication plan provides guidelines for successfully sharing the impacts and benefits of the project with society, transferring knowledge, describing results so they are available for use/re-use and defining concrete actions for that use/re-use.

The aim of this document is to present a clear and coherent dissemination, exploitation and communication strategy which will serve as a cornerstone for all the outreach activities envisaged to be carried out throughout the project thus, ensuring broad communication throughout the project's course. Progress monitoring throughout the project's duration will also be a part of the process.

The deliverable aims to:

- organise the communication flow of the information that will be shared with the project stakeholders and key actors of the NBS/financial community (external environment), as well as the information shared within the BIOFIN-EU partnership (internal environment);
- create the project's brand and unique identity to facilitate the delivery of messages which capture and sustain the target groups' attention constantly and in a comprehensive and gripping manner;
- encourage the audience to act by determining the actions that can have a positive impact on the project and its objectives and
- initiate a framework of rules and recommendations for the successful exploitation and protection of the project's results in terms of commercial use/reuse of the services and tools developed/created within BIOFIN-EU.

This document is the first version of the DEC plan which will be updated to monitor the plan's implementation on M12, M24 & M36 including project advancements and learning sites results. The information will be updated with contributions from all BIOFIN-EU partners, from the monitoring of the progress of the communication and dissemination activities, as well as the exploitation pathways for the project's key results. The deliverable will be finalised by concluding all the dissemination and communication results, their achievement and impact as well as planning for relevant activities after the project ends.

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
BECC	Behaviour Energy and Climate Change
D	Deliverable
DEC	Dissemination Exploitation Communication
EO	Expected Outcome
ES	Ecosystem Services
EU	European Union
FSC	Forest Stewardship Council
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IASB	International Accounting Standards Board
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KERs	Key Exploitable Results
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
LS	learning sites
M	Month
NBS	Nature Based Solutions
NFCs	Non-Financial Corporations
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organisations
RIA	Research and Innovation
SFT	Sustainable Finance Taxonomy
UKRI	United Kingdom Research and Innovation
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

1.1. Project Summary

Challenge

Nature is essential for human existence and our quality of life and society is directly and indirectly dependent on the natural environment, its biodiversity and ecosystem services. We now know that the design of the globalised financial system, which seeks to optimise financial return irrespective of its secondary impacts, is contributing to large-scale biodiversity loss and bringing our biosphere closer to collapse. Yet our modern economics lives are directed by financial institutions and markets. They influence the products we consume (via corporate financing choices), where and how we live (via lending and insurance products), access to energy, food and transport services (via corporate and public enterprise investment) and where we place our savings (via asset management). Behind this front door, the financial system is formed from networks of financial institutions and intermediaries deploying decision-making tools and instruments that direct and redirect the flow of capital. The EU Green Deal and the Sustainable Finance Taxonomy (SFT) provide an important starting point for placing a bound on the destructive power of capital and redirecting financial flows towards nature-positive economic activity.

Aim and approach

BIOFIN-EU's initiative encompasses the development of a pioneering unifying framework and technology designed to create the enabling conditions for large-scale nature-positive investments. Recognizing the complexity of activities that protect and restore biodiversity, such as nature-based solutions (NBS), BIOFIN-EU will establish a categorization of NBS, a menu of effective governance structures, and a comprehensive library of stakeholder engagement strategies. This strategic move will draw on expertise and best practices in natural capital and economics to streamline decision-making, accelerate transaction completion, and standardise the investment process.

BIOFIN-EU's core ambition is to overcome existing boundaries by deploying a science-led cutting-edge data-driven analytics dashboard for nature-positive financial decision support. An underwriting engine to advance project appraisal, risk assessment, and outcome modelling, ushering in a twin green and digital transition to resolve transaction complexity and support the EU in achieving its biodiversity goals.

Consortium

The BIOFIN-EU consortium consists of **13 partners** coming from **10 different countries**. Together all partners form a complete group uniting the necessary expertise, skills, interdisciplinary knowledge and resources capable of achieving the demanding projects goals.

1.2. Document scope and structure

The present Deliverable 7.1 - Dissemination, exploitation communication plan (DEC) (1st version) is developed within the framework of WP7 Impact Maximization. The aim of the deliverable is to integrate the overall dissemination, exploitation and communication strategy of BIOFIN-EU, from day one, to define the goals of DEC activities, to identify the most efficient means to achieve them, and decompose them into a detailed implementation plan. To this end, the DEC plan sets out the objectives, tools, materials, and channels to be exploited in order to effectively spread BIOFIN-EU activities, achievements and tangible results to targeted audiences. Additionally, the BIOFIN-EU DEC plan, also aims to set the pace and a number of foreseen activities in order to place the cornerstone for the successful commercialisation and market uptake of BIOFIN-EU solutions.

This document (D7.1) acts as a reference point to all BIOFIN's partners when carrying out DEC activities related to the project. Delivered in M03, D7.1 will be updated at M12 (version 2), M24 (version 3) and M36 (version 4), presenting progress on reaching Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) as described within.

The document is outlined in 6 chapters, structured to appropriately present the overall BIOFIN-EU DEC objectives, strategy, target audiences, tools and means, channels and material for an efficient and effective implementation of dissemination, communication and exploitation activities within the project lifespan.

This document is comprised of the following 6 chapters:

Chapter 1 provides a summary of the project, the document scope and its overall structure.

Chapter 2 provides an overview of the project's DEC methodology and approach including target groups and key messages and specifies the reporting and monitoring procedures and tools.

Chapter 3 describes BIOFIN-EU's dissemination measures and activities and partner's dissemination KPIs.

Chapter 4 describes BIOFIN-EU's communication measures and activities and partner's communication KPIs.

Chapter 5 describes the BIOFIN-EU's exploitation strategy and project KERs.

Chapter 6 states the overall conclusions.

Annex I present an overview of the D&C reporting tool.

Annex II present the full BIOFIN-EU Brand Book.

Annex III presents the full BIOFIN-EU deliverable template.

Annex IV is the tool created for the identification of new KERs and their IPR process.

2. DEC Methodology and Approach

A strong DEC plan is fundamental for creating lasting impact and will provide a concrete roadmap for partners in order to boost the growth of the BIOFIN-EU ecosystem, raise awareness of project activities and maximise impact among key stakeholders and target groups at the broader social, policy, and industry level. BIOFIN-EU sets clear Communication, Exploitation and Dissemination measures to promote visibility of the project hence more benefits. The plan will follow a targeted multi-actor and multichannel approach with objectives and measures chosen to maximise information dispersal about the project and its results to all identified target groups. It will be intertwined with a sound exploitation strategy, ensuring lasting stakeholder engagement and exploitation of the NBS Dashboard components and project's results.

During the lifespan of the BIOFIN-EU project a tailored multi-channel and multi-dimensional plan for dissemination and exploitation of results including Communication measures (DEC plan) will unfold taking into account GDPR (D1.2 Data Management Plan M6, M18, M36) and Gender equality issues (social and ethical).

2.1. DEC Methodology

The BIOFIN-EU DEC plan is based on the **SOSTAC** model approach¹ which will be considered in every phase of the Dissemination and Communication activities. The SOSTAC model includes the following key elements: **Situation analysis:** A state-of-play analysis which identifies and explains the current challenges to be addressed by the project, the consortium's expertise, the scientific, societal, and economic impacts during and after the project and the potential IPR of the results. A preliminary situation analysis is at the foundation of the DEC plan.

Objectives: The DEC plan will elaborate upon clear and measurable objectives (Section 2.4) that will be achieved through the implementation of communication, dissemination, and exploitation measures.

Strategy: Identification of target groups and key messages for effective communication (Section 2.3).

Figure 1: SOSTAC Methodology

Tactics: Identification of the traditional and digital communication tools and various dissemination activities that will allow the consortium to implement its strategy (Chapters 3 & 4).

¹ SOSTAC® Guide to your Perfect Digital Marketing Plan (2022) (Editor P R Smith) 7th Edition (<https://prsmith.org/books>)

Actions: The DEC plan will build upon the activities, tools and channels defined in the proposal and include the contributions expected from partners, and their distribution over the duration of the project. Preliminary exploitation pathways will be addressed (Chapter 5) and Open Science practices will be factored into all aspects of DEC implementation (Section 3.2.1).

Control: Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) with specific targets determined during the proposal will be used to monitor the progress of the DEC implementation. Templates for partner reporting will also be used along with digital tools for record keeping, all of which will be presented in Section 2.6.

2.2. BIOFIN-EU DEC Time plan

A division of the DEC plan into four phases (Figure 2) is crucial, ensuring both its successful implementation and the achievement of the objectives. The four phases of the DEC plan (Phase 1: Vision, Phase 2: Raise cognition, Phase 3: Multiplier effect, Phase 4: Sustainability) last from the beginning of the project until after its end, enhancing post-project sustainability. Each phase has an overarching objective that will provide focus to activities and create a steady workflow attuned to the work done and results produced by other WPs.

Figure 2: BIOFIN-EU DEC Implementation Time Plan

These measures aim both to highlight the ongoing use and reuse of the project's results and ensure lasting interest and engagement with the project's broader objectives. They will be expanded upon and further developed in the final iteration of the DEC plan. In addition, a multifaceted, sustainability plan with tools to maintain and strengthen the ecosystem, ongoing collaborations and support the forward trajectory of BIOFIN-EU products and solutions will be created as part of the deliverables D7.5-D7.7.

2.3. Target groups and key messages

Six target groups have been identified to categorically define all parties that could have an interest in the project and its results. To summarise the benefit to each group, key messages have been created tailored to target audience's specificities and matching their level of interest (Table 1). General breakdown of activities and channels meant to engage each group has been defined (Table 2). Table 2 will be updated accordingly, if needed, on the second version of the DEC Plan (D7.2) at M12, based on the project's results.

Table 1: Target groups and their key messages

	<p>TG1: Professional Ecosystem</p>
	<p>Members: Auditing firms, Professional education organisations, NFC representative group</p>

Key message: <i>Understand and employ BIOFIN's innovations on Ecosystem restoration/protection and receive training on how to acknowledge and assess the use of NBS</i>	
	TG2: Financial Actors
	Members: Pension and investment managers, private equity firms, venture capital firms, banking and insurance institutions (retail, trust banks), Entrepreneurial Finance.
Key message: <i>Exploit data driven innovations and improved data access to maximise performance, efficiency and stable profit increase</i>	
	TG3: NBS Providers
	Members: 'Internal' NBS (in Non-Financial Corporation, NFCs) and 'External' NBS providers (landowners, farmers, etc)
Key message: <i>Empower decision-making towards NBS with minimum risk and cost transactions</i>	
	TG4: Policy makers & Standardization Bodies
	Members: Public authorities and standardisation organisations (FSC, etc)
Key message: <i>Implement NBS centred policies based on evidence and LS data and monitor / evaluate the sustainability and impact of those policy measures for successful implementation of SFT</i>	
	TG5: Research Organisations
	Members: Universities, students, faculties, and research institutes
Key message: <i>Contribute to cutting edge research in NBS and take advantage of interdisciplinary opportunities and collaborations between similar goal-oriented projects</i>	
	TG6: General Public
	Members: Citizens and their associations, NGOs
Key message: <i>Gain insights on addressing climate challenges associated with biodiversity loss</i>	

Specific communication tools and channels have been scheduled to reach the identified target groups:

Table 2: Communication tools and channels for target audience Channels, tools, and activities

Target Groups						
Communication tools & channels	Professional Ecosystem	Financial Actors	NBS Providers	Policy makers & Standardization Bodies	Research Organisations	General Public
Branding & material	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Website	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓ focus on the society
Social platforms	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓ focus on the society
e-Newsletters	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Multimedia	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Multiplier campaigns	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Scientific Publications	✓	✓		✓	✓	
Technical articles	✓	✓		✓	✓	
Ecosystem Building	✓	✓		✓	✓	
Capacity Building	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Standards & Policy Contribution				✓	✓	

2.4. DEC Objectives and KPIs

BIOFIN-EU will provide a mechanism for a more holistic approach to capital allocation and the mobilisation of mainstream finance towards impactful nature-positive (see Figure 3) by delivering three key tools (*BIOFIN Database*, *BIOFIN Nature-Positive Business Model Builder*, *BIOFIN Data Analytics & Underwriting Engine*) embedded within the NBS Dashboard that will enable impacts to deliver the outcomes specified in the call (detailed below). BIOFIN-EU will also identify policy recommendations that address remaining implementation gaps about how mainstream finance can be redirected to protecting and restoring biodiversity to support the goals of EU Green Deals action plans and EUs biodiversity strategy for 2030. There are an estimated 2 million people employed in the banking sector alone in Europe. The required change in knowledge, skills and processes is enormous and BIOFIN-EU's portfolio of training, business simulation and case studies (*Skills and Knowledge Accelerators*) will be co-designed with target groups: financial institutions,

NFCs; policy makers; researchers; and citizens, to be accessible, flexible and durable. The open access NBS Dashboard will endure beyond the proposed Innovation Action, to 2030. These tools will be used by BIOFIN-EU partners and BIOFIN-EU’s five target groups facilitated and amplified through SUL, IOB and ILSI.

Figure 3: BIOFIN-EU’s contribution towards the Expected Outcome specified in this topic

Dissemination Objectives

The main objective behind the dissemination strategy is to maximise the impact of the project, to increase its visibility, and to ensure that project outputs reach a wide audience of relevant stakeholders.

The plan will follow a targeted multi-actor and multi-channel approach with objectives and measures chosen to maximise information dispersal about the project and its results to all identified target groups. It will be intertwined with a sound exploitation strategy, ensuring lasting stakeholder engagement and exploitation of BIOFIN-EU’s KERs.

BIOFIN-EU applies an intensive dissemination strategy that leads all relevant actions from the very early stages of the project. The intended strategy is aligned with the dissemination objectives as described below:

- Maximise results’ impact
- Facilitate other researchers to advance their research
- Contribute to the advancement of the State of the Art
- Make scientific results a common good

Figure 4: BIOFIN-EU Dissemination KPIs

Communication Objectives

BIOFIN-EU's communication strategy combines a wide but also targeted mechanism for communication actions. Project partners will strategically carry out communication activities through both physical and digital means. RAINNO will create and convey clear tailored and diverse key messages, raise awareness of project activities, enable active engagement, provide efficient dissemination and overall, maximise impact among key stakeholders and target groups at a broader social, policy, and industry level.

BIOFIN-EU's communication strategy has been designed and will be executed, with main focus on informing, promoting and passing all the project's activities to a spectrum of audiences such as citizens, media, investors and relevant stakeholders. Programmed to take place from the start of the project and to ensure that the communication measures will effectively address the project's expectations, communication objectives have been set:

- Raise awareness, facilitate information exchange and capacity building on data-driven sustainability-oriented technology innovations;
- Encourage positive reception and acceptance by financial actors, policy makers & standardisation bodies;
- Reflect gender equality and inclusivity in the approach, tools, and channels;
- Raise awareness on how public money is spent;
- Show the success of European collaboration;
- Market demand generation.

Figure 5: BIOFIN-EU Communication KPIs

Exploitation Objectives

The exploitation refers to the action of making use of and benefiting from project results. Hence, BIOFIN-EU's exploitation activities are recognized as the key enabler for success of the project. All the consortium partners are committed to the exploitation of the project's results and their diverse and complementary research and business contexts provide all potential exploitation modalities and routes to bring BIOFIN-EU's results to all targeted stakeholders. A combination of activities will span throughout the project duration and will vary in intensity, based on the amount of information that can be made available and the results that will be produced during the project's lifetime. The objectives of the project's exploitation measures include:

- Secure positive engagement from relevant stakeholders since it is important to attain both their contributions to the process as well as their willingness to use the results;
- Enhance and facilitate the exploitation of the project's results both by the consortium partners and the stakeholders.

BIOFIN-EU's aims to capture the added value of project results, which will be valorised by:

- Creating feasible paths to deliver project's results to stakeholders interested in their use/reuse;
- Elaborating upon and defining new Key Exploitable Results (KERs) to expedite development and commercialisation when possible.

2.5. Multi-actor approach methodology

The multi-actor approach promotes collaborative, participatory, and solution-oriented approaches to address complex societal challenges and drive positive change. The 'multi-actor' approach is key to the interactive innovation model. Interactive innovation "stresses relations between actors and process"² where the most important resources are the diverse types of knowledge and their links, and interactive learning is the most valuable process. In this context, the multi-actor approach and the way diverse actors work well

² Johannessen, J. A. (2009). A Systemic Approach to Innovation: The Interactive Innovation Model. *Kybernetes*, 38, 158-176. <https://doi.org/10.1108/0368492091093033>

together is central to effectively delivering unique, impactful results. **BIOFIN-EU will use a multi-actor approach**, bringing together all relevant forms of experience and knowledge from a diverse set of partners and stakeholders to appraise, gather, cocreate and disseminate practical solutions to real needs and achieve the project's aims. **Interactive innovation requires a participatory 'bottom-up approach,'** facilitating those at the core of the project to influence project outcomes. This is a social process rather than a 'top-down' scientific approach and also allows members to be involved in the entire development process, from decision-making to evaluation.

Multi-actor interactive innovation brings all the competent actors with various knowledge together, with the aim to plan and codesign practical and implementable solutions to real-life problems. BIOFIN-EU has embodied the multi-actor approach from the inception of the project, following by:

- Targeting real-life needs, challenging current problems, and looking for relevant opportunities.
- Bringing together a consortium with diverse yet complementary knowledge and skills.
- Integrating opportunities to include end users across work packages. BIOFIN's multi-actor co-design methodology will be used to generate tools for the NBS Dashboard (WP2-5) and contribute to policy recommendations (WP6) relating to the SFT.

During the implementation stage, the multi actor approach is fundamental to the project's overall strategy:

- Work packages have clearly defined the roles of partners, and in the context of the DEC plan, clear KPIs and expectations have been established.
- Knowledge exchange activities beyond consortium meetings will be organised at the discretion of task leaders with the support of RAINNO as DEC manager.
- The project management guidelines will ensure opportunities exist for co-creation and co-decision making with partners.

It will also extend to the creation and implementation of the DEC plan, which means:

- Focusing on communicating information that matters to the end user;
- Using language, vocabulary and communication channels that are appealing and audience appropriate;
- Seeking synergies and collaboration opportunities with other projects, initiatives, networks, with and between academia, industry, society and government;
- Capitalising on partners existing connections, networks and events program;
- Including knowledge exchange activities and discussion in event programs.

Key Scenarios

Based upon the *LIAISON project Practitioner Handbook*³, a series of specific scenarios and tools have been identified to ensure interactive innovation and the multi-actor approach are utilised during the project implementation. The handbook will also serve as a reference and additional tools may be utilised.

³ LIAISON (2021) Practitioner Handbook: Evaluation and Impact Assessment of Interactive Innovation. <https://liaison2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/LIAISON-Assessment-Tools.pdf>

Figure 6: BIOFIN-EU multi-actor approach key scenarios

Specific tools have also been selected to achieve the goals of each scenario and have also considered the timing of implementation, the size of the group, resource required and level of technical difficulty.

Scenario 1: ENGAGE

Tool: INTEREST- INFLUENCE MATRIX

This tool helps identify crucial actors that both positively shape the network and those that could negatively influence the network. This helps clearly understand the stakeholders that are the most important for interactive innovation. The tool can be used at multiple times, but the analysis should only be conducted at a given time and repeated to compare results. Figure 7 represents the matrix provided by the LIASON practitioner handbook. The four categories are formed from the relationship between interest of stakeholders and their influence. A best-case scenario is when there is both high interest and influence.

Figure 7: Stakeholder influence, interest matrix

This tool will be used iteratively throughout the project implementation to access and improve networks and collaborations and will particularly be useful for the participatory workshops.

Scenario 2: EXAMINE

Tool: JOURNEY MAPPING

The tool is used to understand the experiences and knowledge of the stakeholders within the project, identifying impacts of the project and their subjective evaluations of the project. The tool intends to assess the extent to which the stakeholder's experiences match with what the project envisaged and intended, pinpointing particular events and experiences.

The journey mapping tool can be used throughout the project implementation.

Scenario 3: CREATE

Tool: GROUND RULES: IDENTIFICATION OF OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES OF AGREEMENT-BASED COOPERATION

The tool is used for assessing cultural norms, held by different actors involved in multi-actor work, which should be respected in the interactive innovation process to enhance how the potential of a diverse group is realised.

The tool has been used during the project development stage, but it can be used iteratively throughout the interactive innovation process.

Scenario 4: ADDRESS

Tool: TRIZ (Theory of Inventive Problem-Solving)

The tool is used for assessing how actors are examining challenges and opportunities in the interactive innovation process and helping them to look at challenges and opportunities from new perspectives as well as engage in new forms of external knowledge to fuel interactive innovation.

TRIZ tool can be used throughout the project implementation whenever new knowledge is required from the outside.

Scenario 5: PLAN

Tool: WHAT, WHO, WHY, WHERE, WHEN & HOW

The tool is used for planning multi-actor tasks in advance, identifying:

- Which actors & stakeholders will be involved – Who?
- The tasks they will be involved in – What?
- Why would they want to be involved in such tasks – Why?
- The logistics and approach of the tasks – Where? When? and How?

It will ensure that the time of partners and stakeholders is well used and will minimise stakeholder fatigue and duplication of tasks.

This tool will be used throughout the implementation of the project.

Scenario 6: EVALUATE

Tool: 'CAUSES AND EFFECTS': BUILDING HYPOTHESES: LINKING ACTIONS TO RESULTS

The tool will help internalise new forms of knowledge and ideas that have been created through brainstorming. The aim will be to help generate hypotheses regarding the cause of effects of actions leading to actions then to results. It also allows participants to continuously reflect and evaluate the decision-making process regarding the choice of project actions, revising and adapting their plans.

The tool will be used throughout the project implementation.

2.6. Planning and reporting procedures

Two main actions for all partners designed in order to plan and report all of their activities:

A. Planning

Partners are asked to provide a plan for their dissemination and communication activities each semester through a dedicated spreadsheet with three tables:

1. BIOFIN-EU Event Planning

Events that are already in the partners organisation's calendar with relevant local, regional and/or national events.

2. BIOFIN-EU Synergy Mapping

Projects that partners are currently involved in. Working groups, networks, alliances that consortium partners are involved in. Other potential synergy opportunities could be foreseen.

3. BIOFIN-EU Publication Planning

Peer reviewed journal publications, industry magazines, white papers, magazine articles and any other publication partners have planned.

1. BIOFIN-EU Event Planning						
Please complete the following form with events that you are already planning on attending over the next 6 months, or any that you are aware of and feel would be well suited for BIOFIN-EU participation.						
#	Name and Type of event	Event link (if applicable)	Date(s) / Location(s)	Scale	Target groups	Potential BIOFIN-EU involvement
	e.g. Conference, Seminar, Webinar, Workshop, Exhibition, etc.		DD/MM/YY / City, Country	e.g. Local, Regional, National, European, International level	The target groups that will attend the event (e.g. Professional Ecosystem, Financial Actors, NBS Providers, Policy makers & Standardization Bodies, Research Organisations, General Public)	e.g. Presentation, Booth, Workshop, Banner ect.

2. BIOFIN-EU Synergy & Liaison mapping						
Please complete the following form with projects, initiatives and/or networks that you are involved with or are aware of and that could provide an opportunity for joint activities and collaboration.						
#	Type of Initiative	Full name	Website	Initiative Leader	Focus area	Potential joint activities
	e.g. Project, Living Lab, Initiative, Working Group	The full name of the initiative		The initiative's main contact or person responsible for the initiative. (e.g. coordinator, project manager) Name and email address.	Provide a brief description of the initiative's focus area or main activity or aim e.g. climate change/mitigation measures and future risks	e.g. Participation in common events, Joint publications, Sharing events on websites ect.

3. BIOFIN-EU Publication Planning			
Please complete the following table with journals, magazines etc. that you intend to publish any progress/results/details of the BIOFIN-EU			
#	Type of publication	Publication website	Estimated submission date
	e.g. Scientific, Technical publication/article, Magazine article, Best practice publication, White/Discussion Paper, Policy/Standards recommendations	Link to the potential journal, magazine, site of publication	

Figure 8: Spreadsheet for planning future events

The spreadsheet (Figure 8) has been uploaded by RAINNO to the project's common folder providing direct and continuous access to partners for updating reasons. Additionally, RAINNO will send monthly reminders to partners to update the forms with relevant information.

B. Reporting

Each month, all partners will be requested to update an online inventory of any communication or dissemination activities and deposit corresponding promoting material such as photos, reports, etc. in a designated folder. This procedure will reinforce accountability and engagement with the dissemination and

communication process. The results will be compiled and serve to monitor targets and inform DEC strategies as the project progresses. RAINNO will be responsible for monitoring the KPIs on a monthly basis and provide updates to the rest of the partners at relevant meetings. In case, significant, or repeated deviations are recorded from certain partners, the coordinator will be officially informed. Deviations will have to be justified, discussed among partners, and changes in the DEC strategy will be reported on the updated versions of the DEC plan.

An online spreadsheet has been developed (**Annex I**) and uploaded on the projects SharePoint (<https://ulcampus.sharepoint.com/sites/BIOFIN>) and is available to all partners. This reporting form is designed for the easy input of dissemination and communication activities and will help maintain accountability and engagement with the dissemination and communication process.

The spreadsheet includes:

- **Sheet: Instructions**, provides instructions on how to use the workbook and important notes regarding the dissemination & communication activities.
- **Sheet 1A: KPI targets per reporting period** and a short description of each KPI.
- **Sheet 2A: the total KPI targets per partner**.
- **Sheet 3A: Monitoring** of the KPI status (overall status, per reporting period and per partner).
- **Sheets 1-13 are dedicated to each partner**, containing one table for reporting the dissemination & communication activities and one table with the overall target for each KPI per partner.

Thus, all partners will be able to provide a detailed report with their monthly D&C Activities, including all the relevant information, such as the place, date and type of an event that have participated or organised, relevant photos, and a drop-down list with all the KPIs, to link each activity with the appropriate KPI category.

3. Dissemination Activities

3.1. Dissemination KPIs

The main objective of the BIOFIN-EU dissemination strategy is to ensure the project’s outcomes, knowledge and opportunities are effectively diffused to the appropriate target communities, making results widely accessible.

Table 3: Dissemination KPIs per partner

	Target	1- UL	2- NAT	3- UGOT	4- UM	5- RAIN	6- SERDA	7- UNIPD	8- ETI	9- IOB	10- SUL	11- ILSI	12- QUB	13- COFAC
PMs	106,7	17	1	1	1	54	5	1	2	0,2	10	8,5	5	1
# Dissemination KPIs														
D.1 Scientific Publications														
D.1.1 Publications in Peer-reviewed journals	12	4	3	2	3									
D.1.2 Publications in scientific conferences	16	3	3	3	3			1		1			2	
D.1.3 Participation in scientific conferences	20	5	3	4	4			1		1			2	
D.2 Technical Articles														
D.2.1 Technical publications/Articles	20	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	1	1		3
D.2.2 White papers	6	2	1		1								2	
D.2.3 Discussion papers	6	1		1				1					2	1
D.2.4 Best practice publications	6	1	1	1	1								2	
D.2.5 Sectoral data & prediction reports	6	1					1	2	1					1
D.3 Ecosystem Building														
D.3.1 Booths at industry fairs, exhibitions and trade shows	3	1									1	1		
D.3.2 Participation in conferences	6	2		1	1					1	1			
D.3.3 Joint events with relevant EU funded projects and initiatives	6	4				2								
D.3.4 Advisory board meetings	2	2												
D.3.5 Scientific / data science workshops and/or webinars	4	1	1										2	
D.3.6 Industry-oriented workshops and/or webinars	10	2		1		1	1		1	1	2		1	
D.3.7 Open days for academic and commercial awareness	10	1	1	1	1		1	1	1		1	1	1	
D.4 Capacity Building														
D.4.1 Co-Creation Workshops ...	20	5	2		1		1	1	1	3			5	1
D.4.2 ... in different countries	6	1	1		1		1						1	1
D.4.3 Online Training Tutorials	15									5	5	5		
D.4.4 Webinars	8	1				1				2	2	2		
D.5 Standards & Policy Contribution														
D.5.1 Reports from the BIOFIN Policy and Implementation Forum	3												3	
D.5.2 Recommendations on accounting standards development	3	2											1	

More specifically, the dissemination strategy’s objectives are to:

- **Capitalise** upon the Learning Sites and raise awareness on the NBS.
- **Promote** synergies with other research, policy and communication initiatives, taking advantage of existing dissemination networks and channels.
- **Engage** targeted audiences to get feedback, validate and ensure broad applicability, replication and scalability of the project's results.
- **Align** and integrate dissemination, communication, ecosystem building activities with exploitation and business modeling processes to allow scale up of outputs.
- **Support** continual exploitation of project results in research, public policy and other relevant driven initiatives.

All partners share the responsibility of communicating the project and disseminating the results. Depending on each partner's expertise, experience, and resource allocation, KPIs and targets were allocated (Table 3).

KPI targets have been distributed across two reporting periods (Table 4) and will be monitored and reported in subsequent DEC plan iterations.

Table 4: Dissemination KPIs per reporting period

#	Dissemination KPIs	Target	Reporting Phases	
			M1-M18	M19-M36
D.1	Scientific Publications			
D.1.1	Publications in Peer-reviewed journals	12	2	10
D.1.2	Publications in scientific conferences	16	4	12
D.1.3	Participation in scientific conferences	20	5	15
D.2	Technical Articles			
D.2.1	Technical publications/Articles	20	5	15
D.2.2	White papers	6	-	6
D.2.3	Discussion papers	6	-	6
D.2.4	Best practice publications	6	1	5
D.2.5	Sectoral data & prediction reports	6	-	6
D.3	Ecosystem Building			
D.3.1	Booths at industry fairs, exhibitions and trade shows	3	1	2
D.3.2	Participation in conferences	6	1	5
D.3.3	Joint events with relevant EU funded projects and initiatives	6	2	4
D.3.4	Advisory board meetings	2	1	1
D.3.5	Scientific / data science workshops and/or webinars	4	1	3
D.3.6	Industry-oriented workshops and/or webinars	10	4	6
D.3.7	Open days for academic and commercial awareness	10	3	7
D.4	Capacity Building			
D.4.1	Co-Creation Workshops in 6 different countries	20	8	12
D.4.2	Online Training Tutorials	15	3	12
D.4.3	Capacity Building Webinars	8	3	5
D.5	Standards & Policy Contribution			
D.5.1	Reports from the BIOFIN <i>Policy and Implementation Forum</i>	3	-	3
D.5.2	Recommendations on accounting standards development	3	-	3

The reporting mechanism (described in Section 2.6) will help maintain accountability and achieve these targets. The first reporting period of the project, regarding both the dissemination and communication (Section 4.1) activities, is fundamental for establishing connections and building interest around the project and will be used to:

- Map stakeholders and their needs that must be addressed;
- Develop the project's website, visual identity, communication materials and social media channels;

- Establish and implement the protocol for deciding events, publications and identifying synergies;
- Begin outreach to other projects, initiatives;
- Participate in events and publish press-releases and newsletters;
- Familiarise partners with all communications channels, templates, and protocols

3.2. Dissemination Measures and Tools

3.2.1. Scientific publications

BIOFIN-EU foresees developing several scientific publications and participating in different scientific conferences, with the purpose of disseminating the research done under the project. All publications will implement Open Access and Open peer-review, in accordance with current EU regulations on Open Access and Open Science.

Open Access

All publications will be published in open-access journals (green or gold). A key aspect for Open Science is to make collected data available for future research and analysis while avoiding the exposure of any personal data without consent. The availability of project outputs as Open Access will ensure:

- Far higher citation counts for academic publications and reports;
- Greater impact due to increased visibility with practitioners and the wider stakeholder community;
- Higher likelihood that future research and analysis will be able to build on and reuse BIOFIN-EU's results thereby helping in terms of the reproducibility and continuity of research results.

Procedures

With regards to publications, partners are requested to fill in the Publication Planning Template, which is part of the event planning spreadsheet (Figure 8), so there is good tracking of what will be published and when. Moreover, with regards to publications (and presentations), during the project and for a period 1 year after the end of the project all partners are obliged to comply with the rules specified in the Grant Agreement. This includes:

- Prior notice of any planned publication should be given to the other parties at least forty-five calendar days before the publication.
- Any objection to the planned publication should include a precise request for necessary modifications and be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement by written notice to the coordinator and to the party or parties proposing the dissemination within thirty calendar days after receipt of the notice.
- If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, publication is permitted.

An objection is justified, and measures will be taken to overcome the objection if:

- The protection of the objecting party's results or background would be negatively affected, or
- The objecting party's legitimate interests in relation to its results or background would be significantly harmed, or
- The proposed publication includes confidential Information of the objecting party.

In addition, the unpublished results or background of any partner will not be used for dissemination purposes without obtaining the owning party's prior written approval.

3.2.1.1. Publications in Peer-reviewed journals

BIOFIN-EU aims to publish at least **12 peer-reviewed journals** in respected and highly rated journals and scientific magazines. Scientific publications are one of the key means of disseminating the project's results to the research community and providing scientific credibility for the project's work. This task has been undertaken mostly by the university and research partners (UL, NAT, UGOT, UM) and publications cover several fields of the work performed within the BIOFIN-EU project.

3.2.1.2. Publications in scientific conferences

Research partners (UL, NAT, UGOT, UM, UNIPD, IOB, QUB) will also strive to publish **16 conference papers** in different relevant academic conferences. Those publications will help again in disseminating the project's results to the research community.

3.2.1.3. Participation in scientific conferences

BIOFIN-EU partners will also participate in at least **20 scientific conferences** with the purpose of networking, stay in touch with the latest research relevant to the project and seeking strategic collaborations. The partners that will undertake this KPI are UL, NAT, UGOT, UM, UNIPD, IOB, and QUB.

3.2.2. Technical Articles

3.2.2.1. Technical publications/articles

Besides the creation of scientific publications, BIOFIN-EU will publish at least **20 technical publications/articles** to high quality technical blog posts, articles, catalogues, books or any other reference from technology providers (bottom-up) as well as references related to the application scenarios domains under consideration (top-down) will be developed to make the project and its results known to industrial stakeholders.

3.2.2.2. White Papers and Discussion Papers

To achieve high-scale and long-lasting impact, BIOFIN-EU aims to provide in-depth analyses, strategies, and recommendations via the publication of **6 white papers** with the common conceptual model for BIOFIN-EU and relevant standards to ensure greater clarity and precision of what the concept entails and what is required for it to be deployed successfully as well as **6 discussion papers** with contributions from research organisations, industry and standardisation bodies.

3.2.2.3. Best Practice Publications

BIOFIN will produce **6 best practice publications**, in the form of summaries for practitioners, dedicated to BIOFIN's activities and outcomes such as the 8 Learning Sites, Accounting Standards, Business Models and other. The goal is to develop short summaries that describe the main information/recommendation/practice regarding the deployment of the NBS Dashboard that will help actors navigate large-scale financing challenges and to develop, replicate, scale out and strengthen NBS-investment.

3.2.2.4. Sectoral data and prediction reports

BIOFIN-EU will produce **6 Sectoral data & prediction reports** that will provide data-driven insights and predictions about relevant innovations and research derived from project activities and the 8 Learning Sites.

3.2.3. Ecosystem Building

BIOFIN-EU recognizes ecosystem building as essential in order to create impact. The BIOFIN-EU consortium partners aim in building a collaborative ecosystem by promoting multi-actor procedures therefore, to bring together, learn each other's stories and experiences and ultimately empower key organisations to share information seamlessly with one another and work together.

To achieve this above-mentioned goal, BIOFIN-EU has primarily set up and will collaborate with an **external Advisory board**, with 8 members from the research, ecology insurance and agri-food industry domains, that will provide comments and advice about NBS/SFT domain-related, human-related and political-related issues in the context of the ongoing project.

Furthermore, the BIOFIN-EU consortium will enhance its ecosystem-building activities and therefore come closer to the fields of nature-based solutions and mainstream finance. Partners will participate with BIOFIN-EU booths in relevant commercial and trade events, organise scientific and industry-oriented events (webinars, workshops etc.), participate in conferences and organise dedicated sessions in relevant events and initiatives (e.g. BECC, IPCC).

Ecosystems involve diverse voices—more expertise and perspectives. By tapping into this collective wisdom, tangible, effective solutions emerge. Rather than isolating discussions within one department, ecosystems foster collaboration, leading to better outcomes. This will be done by a series of ecosystem activities that will include: **3 booths at industry fairs, exhibitions and trade shows, 6 participations in conferences, 6 joint events with relevant EU-funded projects and initiatives, 2 advisory board meetings, 4 scientific/data science workshops and/or webinars, 10 industry-oriented workshops and/or webinars and 10 open days for academic and commercial awareness.**

3.2.3.1. Links to other projects

BIOFIN builds on and links to a range of projects past and current, which have complementary goals. Through extensive communication activities through partner networks and events and a dedicated task (T6.3, T7.1-T7.3) BIOFIN-EU will exploit synergies with relevant successful HORIZON CL6-2023 project(s) to further consider best practice in upscaling and multifunctionality.

Table 5: Relevant projects

Project (BIOFIN Partner)	Link to BIOFIN
Burren Beo Programme (UL)	This innovative programme uses a scorecard system and linked payments to results achieved by farmers. UL (via HNVS) has full access to historical scorecard data (biodiversity, ES outcomes), results-based payments and participating farmers to develop new insights into economic valuations of benchmark and categorise data for Dashboard feeding into WP3-5 to meet EO1-3.
Connecting Nature (ETI, SERDA)	It is an RIA led by 29 stakeholders from local authorities, communities, industry partners, NGOs and academics that aims to restore and protect biodiversity in cities. Provides access to NBS (providers and funders), co design so <i>The NBS Dashboard</i> modules can be integrated to help scale up 'deal size' on nature-positive investments on the Connecting Nature Enterprise Platform (WP2-WP6), LS#8

SINCERE (UNIPD, ETIFOR)	Develops novel policies and new business models for forest ecosystem services. BIOFIN extends expertise on multifunctional forest economy and ES and focuses on creating channels for large-scale finance via standardised modes for capturing and sharing data through the financial system.
INCREDIBLE (UNIPD)	Offers networks for Mediterranean Non-Wood Forest Products (NWFPs) that foster innovation in science and practice exchange. <i>The NBS Dashboard</i> helps create two-way channels connecting science and practice in production, and financial decision-making (lending, investment) for NWFPs.
LIFE ProForPES (UNIPD)	Promoting effective forest through PES through the EU financial and state aid programmes. Data and access to participants will provide insights into the payment for ES, a starting point for the development of SFT aligned tools and instruments that can reduce the bottlenecks for large-scale private finance (rather than state aid framework).
LIFE Brenta 2030 (UNIPD, ETI)	The area of the Middle Brenta has been included among the Natura 2000 sites . Analysis of activity categorisation and emergent novel financial instruments and governance structures to scale up restoration and protection activities is the focus of LS#6.
LIFE IP gESTIRE 2020 (UNIPD, ETI)	Focused on developing policies and management actions for the Natura 2000 regional network. Project outcomes and insights will contribute to the architecture of <i>The NBS Dashboard</i> and access to historical data via ETI and UNIPD will contribute to the <i>Data Analytics and Underwriting Engine</i> .
FILECOIN.io (UM)	BIOFIN researcher Dr. Ashish Sai work will contribute to the architecture of the Dashboard so that it accounts for the particular challenges associated with complex, heterogenous NBS data in order to reduce barriers to large-scale 'nature-positive' investment. WP4 (T4.2, T4.3)
DiTECT (UM)	Focuses on digital technologies as an enabler of continuous transformation of food safety systems. The NBS Dashboard is similarly aiming to deploy digital technologies to lower implementation barriers of the SFT, identify gaps in the criteria/sectors that are preventing 'nature-positive' investment.
FRIBO (QUB, UL)	A UKRI funded project on Financial Rewards for improved biodiversity outcomes provides extensive access to financial institutions and NFCs as well as a network of researchers that are focused on how to unlock the innovative capacity in the financial system.
FINIFOR (UL, QUB)	Provides insights into the requirements to design a long-horizon (25+ years) financial instrument - including insurance components (e.g. ES decline due to disease, wildfire), implications of tax and agricultural policy on landowners' behaviour and participation in NBS, institutional and cultural barriers to adoption (peer group behaviours, land productivity, real option/flexibility valuations).

HESI (SUL)	Funded by the UN, the Higher Education Sustainability Initiative provides a sustainability literacy examination tool. SUL will integrate BIOFIN data, tools and methodologies into the assessment and curriculum across a range of subject areas, including <i>corporate finance, financial institutions and markets, accounting and auditing frameworks, modern portfolio theory, wealth and portfolio management</i> .
EUREKA EU Farmbook (UM)	A single user-friendly platform to help get practical knowledge into the hands of the farmers, foresters and advisors across Europe, this forms a key R&I foundation of BIOFIN. Link: Awarded to BIOFIN partner, UM meaning free and full access to all methods, knowledge and experience gleaned from it which will feed into WP2-4.
Other relevant European Projects: TITAN (Project Coordinator: ILSI; Partner: QUB) and SUS-HEALTH (QUB) aim to enhance food transparency and labelling to account for environmental impact .	

3.2.4. Capacity Building

Capacity building is crucial for the success of a project as it enhances the skills and knowledge of individuals and organisations involved. This leads to improved performance, adaptability to change, and a culture of innovation. It increases confidence and motivation, fostering sustainability by ensuring that teams can support and maintain project outcomes over the long term. It also facilitates better stakeholder engagement, risk mitigation, and optimal resource use. Additionally, knowledge transfer within partners and stakeholders is promoted, reducing the risk of dependency on a few individuals and contributing to overall project resilience and success.

Capacity building also enables individuals to enhance their skills and knowledge. This personal growth can lead to better overall personal and professional development. BIOFIN-EU will build capacity in skills development for current professional bankers and investment managers as well as the next generation of business leaders in European business schools. This will be achieved through **20 co-creation Workshops in 6 different countries, 15 online training tutorials and 8 webinars**.

3.2.5. Standards & Policy Contribution

BIOFIN-EU will strive to influence ecology and ecosystem standard settings in order to create the enabling conditions for large-scale private finance and explore requirements and pathways for new accounting standards relating to proactive biodiversity investment (e.g. via IASB) The project partners will also try to push acquired knowledge into production environments and define future financial directions. For this aim the partners will produce **3 reports from the BIOFIN-EU Policy and Implementation Forum, and 3 recommendations on accounting standards development**.

3.3. EC tools

BIOFIN-EU will take advantage of several of the tools offered by the European Commission to support dissemination (D), exploitation (E) and communication (C) of the project's results.

Figure 9: EC Tools

4. Communication Activities

4.1. Communication KPIs

BIOFIN-EU aims to raise public awareness of the project through a range of strategically planned actions that are accessible to internal and external stakeholders, the media and the general public and will:

- **Communicate impacts and benefits** of the project and its results for the duration of the project and after, by integrating various activities, tools and channels.
- **Customise communication activities** for different target groups as well as subgroups within.

Table 6: Communication KPIs per partner

	Target	1- UL	2- NAT	3- UGOT	4- UM	5- RAIN	6- SERDA	7- UNIPD	8- ETI	9- IOB	10- SUL	11- ILSI	12- QUB	13- COFAC	
PMs	106,7	17	1	1	1	54	5	1	2	0,2	10	8,5	5	1	
#	Communication KPIs	Target													
C.1 Branding & material															
C.1.1	Visual identity	1				1									
C.1.2	Logo	1				1									
C.1.3	Design of banners (>1 per LS and >1 for the project)	9				9									
C.1.4	Design of brochures (>1 per LS and >1 for the project)	9				9									
C.1.5	Printing and distribution of promotional materials - brochures	7000	2000	300	600	600	300	300	300	350	850	550	250		
C.2 Website															
C.2.1	website	1				1									
C.2.2	Unique visitors	5000				5000									
C.2.3	Blog posts	50				50									
C.3 Social Platforms															
C.3.1	Social media channels (Linkedin, Youtube, Facebook, Twitter, Slideshare)	5				5									
C.3.2	Social Media Audience	2000				2000									
C.3.3	Posts	200				200									
C.3.4	Monthly impressions	400				400									
C.3.5	hashtags to use in social media	5				5									
C.3.6	share of highly relevant articles/ per month >2	72				72									
C.4 e-Newsletters															
C.4.1	e-newsletters	15				15									
C.4.2	subscriptions	1000				1000									
C.4.3	interactions	800				800									
C.4.4	highly relevant articles/ per e-newsletter	10				10									
C.5 Multimedia															
C.5.1	Published videos (>1 for each pilot and >2 for the project)	10	1			2	1	1	2					3	
C.5.2	Podcast series (10 episodes each) in Google or Spotify podcasts app	2				2									
C.6 Multiplier campaigns															
C.6.1	Press releases	8				8									
C.6.2	Published articles in online platforms and offline media	10				10									

BIOFIN-Eu's communication plan is a crucial component for:

- Raising awareness regarding the potential contribution of its nature-based solutions to the empowerment of the finance industry towards biodiversity protection and restoration investments,
- democratising knowledge, and
- attracting target groups and the general audience to solutions addressing urgent social and environmental challenges.

All partners share the responsibility of communicating the project and disseminating the results. Depending on each partner's expertise, experience, and resource allocation, KPIs and targets were allocated (Table 6).

KPI targets have been distributed across two reporting periods (Table 7) and will be monitored and reported in subsequent DEC plan iterations.

Table 7: Communication KPIs per reporting period

#	Communication KPIs	Target	Reporting Phases	
			M1-M18	M19-M36
C.1 Branding & material				
C.1.1	Visual identity	1	1	-
C.1.2	Logo	1	1	-
C.1.3	Design of banners (>1 per LS and >1 for the project)	9	9	-
C.1.4	Design of brochures (>1 per LS and >1 for the project)	9	9	-
C.1.5	Printing and distribution of promotional materials - brochures	7000	2000	5000
C.2 Website				
C.2.1	website	1	1	-
C.2.2	Unique visitors	5000	2000	3000
C.2.3	Blog posts	50	25	25
C.3 Social Platforms				
C.3.1	Social media channels (Linkedin, Youtube, Facebook, Twitter, Slideshare)	5	5	-
C.3.2	Social Media Audience	2000	700	1300
C.3.3	Posts	200	100	100
C.3.4	Monthly impressions	400	400	400
C.3.5	hashtags to use in social media	5	5	-
C.3.6	share of highly relevant articles/ per month >2	72	36	36
C.4 e-Newsletters				
C.4.1	e-newsletters	15	7	8
C.4.2	subscriptions	1000	400	600
C.4.3	interactions	800	300	500
C.4.4	highly relevant articles/ per e-newsletter	10	5	5
C.5 Multimedia				
C.5.1	Published videos (>1 for each pilot and >2 for the project)	10	1	9
C.5.2	Podcast series (10 episodes each) in Google or Spotify podcasts app	2	-	2
C.6 Multiplier campaigns				
C.6.1	Press releases	8	3	5
C.6.2	Published articles in online platforms and offline media	10	4	6

4.2. Communication Measures and Tools

4.2.1. Branding & Material

4.2.1.1. Visual identity

BIOFIN-EU's communication material aims to promote and simultaneously increase stakeholder and public awareness of the project. To multiply the sphere of influence, both digital and physical forms have been created. Offline communication products have the added advantage of being physical, tangible and will occupy space to captivate audiences during the project's participation in events and conferences. These materials focus on a more visually engaging way of raising awareness about the project's aims, activities and results. It is advantageous to follow certain rules when utilising offline material – regardless of the implementation strategies; well-prepared headlines, wisely colours usage, focus on benefits – and keep the tone and the message aligned to the intended target audience.

Brand Book

To achieve this goal, all of the aforementioned will align with **BIOFIN-EU's brand book** (Figure 10), to ensure that the produced communication material aligns with the project's visual identity and the branding guidelines. The full version of the BIOFIN-EU brand book is presented in **Annex II**.

Figure 10: BIOFIN-EU Brand Book

4.2.1.2. Templates

Because BIOFIN-EU will be presented at numerous events, conferences, meetings as well as other occasions to disseminate project developments and results, a **presentation template (ppt)** (Figure 11), as well as a **word (doc) template** (Figure 12), have been designed in line with BIOFIN-EU graphic identity in order to maintain consistency, professionalism and promote its recognition. Additionally, more templates have been

designed for several events purposes such as an events **minute's template** and an **agenda template** (Figures 13 & 14).

Figure 11: BIOFIN-EU Presentation Template

Figure 12: BIOFIN-EU Word Template

Figure 13: BIOFIN-EU Minutes Template

Figure 14: BIOFIN-EU Agenda Template

BIOFIN-EUs **deliverable template** (Figure 15) is also consistent with communication and dissemination material graphic identity and will be used by the consortium partners for the development of all project deliverables. The deliverable template has a cover page that displays the project’s logo in a prominent position, its acronym, deliverable information (number, full title, the work package number and title) as well as the writer’s information. For the full version of the deliverable template see **Annex III**.

BIOFIN-EU

PROTECTING AND RESTORING BIODIVERSITY USING MAINSTREAM FINANCE

DX.X: [Deliverable Title]

Lead Author: [Author Name and Surname (Partner)]

Funded by the European Union

BIOFIN EU

DX.X: Deliverable Title

Grant Agreement No.	101135476
Project Acronym	BIOFIN-EU
Project Title	Protecting and Restoring Biodiversity using Mainstream Finance
Type of action	HORIZON-RIA
Horizon Europe Call Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2023-BIODIV-01-9
Start – ending date	1 January 2024 – 31 December 2026
Project Website	biofin-project.eu
Work Package	WPx: Title of the WP
WP Lead Beneficiary	Partner's full name (Short name)
Relevant Task(s)	Tx.x Title of the Task
Deliverable type Dissemination level	R – Report; DEC: Websites, press & media actions, videos, etc; OTHER: Software, etc. PU: Public; SEN: Sensitive; CI: Classified
Due Date of Deliverable	DD Month 20YY
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biofin-project.eu Page | 2

Figure 15: BIOFIN-EU Deliverable Template

EU Emblem

All BIOFIN-EU dissemination and communication material will acknowledge the requirements set out by the European Commission and include the EU flag and the source of funding, based on Article 17.2 “Visibility-European flag and funding statement” of the Grant Agreement (Figure 16).

Figure 16: EU Emblem

Disclaimer for publications

In addition to the EU Emblem, all dissemination and communication material must include the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

The disclaimer and acknowledgement of EU funding should be on the cover or the first pages following the editor’s mention.

All research publications will include an acknowledgement of Horizon EU funding and the following disclaimer:

"Funding for this research has been provided by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme BIOFIN-EU (Grant Agreement Number 101135476). Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."

4.2.1.3. Logo

The logo is the main tool to create direct visual recognition of the BIOFIN-EU project, therefore, was chosen to be simple, give a hint of a story but above all to be easily recognizable. The BIOFIN-EU logo showcases the acronym using a clear and modern font. BIOFIN-EU's logo is composed of three parts (Figure 17). On top, a graph chart arrow going up with leaves growing on it, representing ecological and sustainable growth. Below the arrow, BIOFIN-EU's acronym is presented using two different colours. The logo will also be used in all internal and external communication and dissemination activities (project website, presentations, flyers, press releases etc.) to help enhance brand continuity and raise awareness, throughout the project's lifetime and beyond. The most frequently used logo for most of the communication and dissemination material is shown in Figure 17 below:

Figure 17: BIOFIN-EU Logo

4.2.1.4. Roll-up Banner

BIOFIN-EU's roll-up banners will be used to promote the project, as well as the learning sites at physical events, for eye-catching identification of the BIOFIN-EU booth. The first banner of the project has already been designed (Figure 18), while the other **eight** (one for each learning site) are planned. The general project's banner includes the most important information related to the BIOFIN-EU, the motto of the project, the social media accounts, as well as a QR code, which leads to the project website providing direct access to the project's scope and activities.

Figure 18: BIOFIN-EU Banner

4.2.1.5. Brochures

Brochures will be designed for online distribution and at physical events. The first brochure presenting the project mission, methodology, consortium and expected results (Figure 19) is already designed. The other **eight** brochures will be dedicated to the learning sites.

Figure 19: BIOFIN-EU Brochure

4.2.1.6. Other

Other communication materials that could be used to attract a wider audience include folders, notebooks, pens, magnets, and bags. Examples of potential communication material can be found in **Annex II** as part of the Brand book. All material must be in line with the project’s visual identity (use of defined colour palettes and styles).

4.2.2. Website

BIOFIN-EU's website (www.biofin-project.eu) has already been developed. The project's website is the primary communication and dissemination platform to enable target groups and BIOFIN-EU's stakeholders to access project development and results, and to grasp and assess the added value and the impact of nature-positive financial decision support. The website will be updated frequently and will utilise input from all partners. It will provide an overview of the learning sites, partners and links to their websites and it will host all the public dissemination deliverables, promote relevant content (news, editorials, videos, workshops, press releases, printed material, publications etc.) for key stakeholder groups, thus engaging them in the content and objectives of the project. It will also host digital visualisations of project processes and results, to make them accessible to a wider audience. Finally, the website will also be mobile-friendly, increasing accessibility and maximising the impact of the project (Figure 20).

Figure 20: BIOFIN-EU Website on mobile and desktop

BIOFIN-EU's website has a twofold role as it will serve as the principal reference point for the project, explaining the project's aims, providing new updates, and documents for download and enabling access to social media accounts of BIOFIN-EU. Furthermore, it will act as a resource centre for research on topics related to NBS, providing important updates that have an impact.

Delivered in M3, the BIOFIN-EU website is hosted at <https://biofin-project.eu/> and contains the following sections and features:

1. **Home/Landing page:** Includes the project logo, project graphics, social media icons (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, SlideShare), a button for sign-up in the BIOFIN-EU's newsletter, BIOFIN-EU's Objectives and expected results, all partners logos, EU's Emblem. The main contact information for the coordinator and communication manager will be provided at the bottom as well as the cookies and privacy policy.

2. **About:**

- Objectives,
- NBS Dashboard,
- Partners

3. **Learning Sites:** Includes descriptions of the Learning Sites

4. **News & Events**

- Blog (Press releases and blog posts will be the main content and will inform stakeholders of all project's activities)
- Events (All the events that BIOFIN-EU partners have organised or participated in)

5. **Resources**

- Press Kit
- Videos
- Podcast
- Publication
- Deliverables
- Newsletters

6. **Synergies**

7. **Contact:** All contact information for the BIOFIN-EU project will be available under this section enabling the easiest communication with our stakeholders through email and a contact form for messages. In addition, the visitor can find links to all the social media accounts of the projects.

8. **Subscribe Button:** A dedicated button that redirects visitors to the subscription page for the BIOFIN-EU newsletter.

9. **Cookies & Privacy Policy:** The Cookies Policy, together with the Privacy Policy has also been included in the BIOFIN-EU website, set for the general rules and policies governing the visitors' use of the website.

To ensure the proper visibility of the website and monitor the relevant KPIs, the platform "Google Analytics" has been used, which is a well-established web analytics tool provided by Google and tracks website traffic. Although Google Analytics provides a wide range of metrics to track, we focus on the website's unique visitors, i.e. new users (Figure 21).

Figure 21: BIOFIN-EU Website Metrics Overview

4.2.3. Social Media Platforms

To apply the multi-actor approach and establish two-way communication with the audience, BIOFIN-EU aims to have a strong social media presence. **Five media channels** (LinkedIn, YouTube, Facebook, Twitter, and Slideshare) were selected based on the following factors:

- The most cost-effective set of channels for sharing immediate updates from the project to all stakeholder groups;
- The most adequate, valid and powerful media channels for spreading and influencing with novel practices, a wide spectrum and several key stakeholders;
- The most popular social media platforms used by BIOFIN-EU's partners, to communicate and interact with their customers and other stakeholders.

Since the M1 of the project, BIOFIN-EU has been active on social media platforms (LinkedIn, Youtube, Facebook, Twitter, Slideshare) targeting to reach a diverse audience and connect with potential stakeholders who may prefer one platform over another. Each social media channel is individually presented in upcoming sections.

When it comes to content creation, there are several parameters to consider for BIOFIN-EU's social media:

- **Consistency** is the main pillar of our social media strategy, maintaining a consistent brand identity by using consistent colours tones and messaging to make BIOFIN-EU easily recognizable. Also, in terms of frequency, a constant and active appearance on social media boosts the project's visibility and attracts new followers;
- **Authenticity** is crucial in BIOFIN-EU social media profiles. That's why we share genuine content that reflects the BIOFIN-EU project;
- **Eye-catching posts** lead to higher conversions with the prioritisation of high-quality images, videos, and graphics that are visually appealing and consistent with the BIOFIN-EU brand. All the material is designed in a way that can be easily understood even without sound on (especially referring to videos);
- **Content** that is value-driven and characterised by **variety**. The BIOFIN-EU posts can be in the form of informative content, entertainment, or inspiration. This makes it more likely for people to engage with the content and share it;

- **Call to Action (CTA).** Encouraging our audience to take action, whether it's liking, sharing, commenting or visiting the BIOFIN-EU website, can drive engagement.

The aforementioned are summed up and visually presented in the figure below (Figure 22).

Figure 22: Content of the BIOFIN-EU's social media posts

To maximise the project's visibility and impact, BIOFIN-EU exploits the consortium's already-developed social media networks. Consortium's partners are expected to share, publish and retweet content from the BIOFIN-EU social media accounts and BIOFIN-EU website, thus, increasing traction for project-related work and increasing traffic on partner's websites and social media. Partners are also encouraged to create relevant content for the project's actions and share it through their channels. Social media accounts were collected from all partners at the beginning of the project, to enhance BIOFIN-EU's online visibility by creating a social network and promoting BIOFIN-EU's activities and results.

In order to monitor the social media accounts and ensure their effectiveness, a number of metrics have been tracked, in line with the KPIs targets claimed in the Grant Agreement. Measuring our social media audience provides valuable insights into the effectiveness of our social media strategy and the visibility of the project.

4.2.3.1. LinkedIn

A [LinkedIn profile](#) was created to network with BIOFIN-EU target audiences and promote the project's activities. As such, all project news will be published on LinkedIn profile and partners will have the opportunity to start conversations on particular themes and attract a wider audience. Figure 23 provides an overview of BIOFIN-EU's LinkedIn profile.

Figure 23: BIOFIN-EU LinkedIn page

4.2.3.2. Facebook

BIOFIN-EU’s [Facebook page](#) was developed to communicate directly with target audiences on an individual level (Figure 24).

Figure 24: BIOFIN-EU Facebook page

4.2.3.3.X (Twitter)

An [X\(Twitter\) account](#) was created to increase the visibility of the project and engage specific audiences such as policymakers and advisors. BIOFIN-EU will use short messages (less than 280 characters) to interact and post news, events and updates on the project's status (Figure 25).

Twitter's popularity and concise, simple format make it extremely important and useful for informing and engaging with our targeted audiences and their respective communities. Twitter will also be used to connect to "high influencers" in the research and business topics of the BIOFIN-EU project to successfully build an active community.

Figure 25: BIOFIN-EU Twitter profile

4.2.3.4. Youtube

A [YouTube channel](#) will be used in order to host and promote BIOFIN-EU’s videos, which will be of wide variety, such as interviews, case studies, demos etc. BIOFIN-EU’s YouTube channel will be mainly used for awareness and training purposes, focusing on all BIOFIN-EU’s target groups and every stakeholder interested in food safety, AI and data mining applications (Figure 26).

Figure 26: BIOFIN-EU YouTube channel

4.2.3.5. SlideShare

A [SlideShare account](#) has been created to present project material in an engaging visual format that appeals to BIOFIN-EU’s audience. Project presentations will be available for any interested stakeholder providing key information on the project implementation and activities (Figure 27).

Figure 27: BIOFIN-EU SlideShare account

4.2.3.6. Hashtags

Creating hashtags relevant to the project and its outcomes will help reach target audiences and make it easy to find BIOFIN-EU generated knowledge. Hashtags divide the project’s main topics into easily digestible and engaging keyword phrases and will help increase visibility in the social media environment, while they will

make BIOFIN-EU’s messages stand out and influence relevant communities. Further tracking of the hashtags will facilitate the consortium to analyse quantitative and qualitative data. The project has set five official distinctive hashtags (in line with the Communication KPIs of the Grant Agreement), which are **#biodiversity**, **#nature**, **#greenfinance**, **#sustainablefinance**, **#sustainability** (Figure 28). These hashtags have been chosen among a list of 9 hashtags as the most relevant by the consortium, during the Kick-off meeting, in Brussels (Belgium) on 8-9 February 2024. Additionally, two more hashtags are always considered: **#HorizonEU** and **#ResearchImpactEU**. Finally, other hashtags will occasionally be used, considering the respective content of the posts each time.

Figure 28: BIOFIN-EU hashtags

4.2.4.e-Newsletters

An online newsletter will be published every 4 months (starting M04) to provide updates and relevant information to subscribers and consortium members. This will include the latest developments, use case results and activities, and where to find recent reports and publications. Also, there will be additional newsletter issues as “special editions”, and announcements for upcoming events, workshops and demonstrations.

Subscriptions can take place at events as well as in BIOFIN-EU’s website (Figure 29). Upon Newsletter registration, BIOFIN-EU will pay special attention to security and respect of the privacy and confidentiality of the user’s personal data. Newsletter recipients will be asked to provide their consent prior to sending any information related to the project. All relevant activities and aspects related to personal data will be fully compliant with the applicable national, European, and international legal framework, and the European Union’s General Data Protection Regulation 2016/6798. Interested parties will be able to subscribe and unsubscribe at any given point from the BIOFIN-EU Newsletters and all collected data will be stored and saved in the responsible partner’s servers. Users’ data will be inaccessible to third parties. A more detailed description of data collection, storage and handling will be presented in the respective deliverables (D1.2 – Data Management Plan M6, D1.3 – Data Management Plan Update M18, D1.4 – Data Management Plan Final M36). Professional marketing platforms (i.e., Mailchimp) will be used to automate the distribution among contact points. Furthermore, to achieve broader distribution and facilitate the engagement of as many stakeholders as possible, BIOFIN-EU partners will be encouraged to promote newsletters to their contacts who may be interested in the project.

Figure 29: Subscription form on the website

The first issue of the newsletter will be released in April 2024 (M04), drafted and designed by RAINNO, and will be approved by the coordinator, while the content will be provided by the partners. All the issues of the newsletter will be distributed to the subscribers and uploaded on the project’s website. In parallel, the issues will be promoted on the project’s social media pages, via “call to action” and informative posts, before and after their release, respectively. There is a specific plan for the distribution of the BIOFIN-EU newsletter, in terms of release frequency and number of issues (Figure 30). The “Special Edition” issues, as well as, the event announcements will be launched based on the project’s progress and results, thus it is not possible to plan them beforehand.

Figure 30: Newsletter plan

In total at least **15 e-newsletters** will be published in the span of the project, which will also contain at least **10 highly relevant articles each**, anticipating **1.000 newsletter subscribers** and **800 interactions** over the course of the project. The structure of the newsletter is standardised, however, small changes can be made contextually:

- Introduction of the project
- Project Update / Key news and project events
- Dedicated section to a partner (when applicable)
- Resources for further reading (suggested by all partners)

The newsletter is open even for non-subscribers and all the issues can be found on the project's website in the dedicated section.

4.2.5. Multimedia

4.2.5.1. Published videos

Due to its flexibility, video can be a highly effective marketing tool that businesses can utilise to their advantage. By developing videos of the BIOFIN-EU project as well as evidence/results-based videos of the learning sites it is anticipated that interest and enquiries from BIOFIN-EU's target audiences will be generated. At least **10 videos** will be produced and published, 1 for each learning site and 2 for the overall project), all videos will be uploaded onto the BIOFIN-EU website and YouTube channel.

4.2.5.2. Podcast series

Podcasts are digital audio files presented in a series, typically with new instalments received automatically by subscribers. This on-demand technology is growing in popularity with 464.7 million podcast listeners globally as of 2023⁴. BIOFIN-EU will create **2 podcast series of ten episodes each**, to enrich and diversify the website and address auditory learning styles. Content created by partners will follow an overarching theme that will make for a cohesive, entertaining series. The length of each episode will be around 10-15 minutes. The podcast series will be developed during months 19-36 and will be organised by RAINNO.

Two podcast categories will be designed to focus on the following categories:

- Interviews of the consortium partners, project advancements and results, and future directions.
- Capacity building on sustainable finance and nature-positive investments.

4.2.6. Multiplier Campaigns

A multiplier campaign combines several communication and dissemination strategies that reinforce a message to obtain a greater positive impact. To this end, BIOFIN-EU will broaden the scope of communication tools and channels to include press releases and articles published in online platforms and offline media. These additional channels will add credibility and visibility and connect with local and regional networks.

4.2.6.1. Press Releases

Press releases will be produced and distributed for publication among national/regional/EU press to further promote the project, its latest activities and developments to a broader audience as well as addressing more specific stakeholders. To maximise influence on local stakeholders, the consortium is advised to translate all press releases into all consortium partners' languages (Figure 31). More specifically, the first press release was developed after BIOFIN-EU's kick-off meeting which took place at M2 and distributed to consortium members and various digital media, such as [Oppla](#) and [Network Nature](#) (Figure 32). The target that we aim to achieve until the end of the project is **8 press releases in total**.

4

<https://www.demandsage.com/podcast-statistics/#:~:text=There%20are%20464.7%20million%20podcast,podcast%20listeners%20in%20the%20world.>

Figure 31: The first BIOFIN-EU press release

Figure 32: The BIOFIN-EU press release on relevant platforms

4.2.6.2. Published articles on online platforms and offline media

Consortium partners will leverage print (newspapers, magazines) and online media (such as blogs) related to the researched topics of the project, to maximise the project's impact and engage stakeholders outside the prioritised target groups. BIOFIN-EU will publish and contribute at least **10 articles** on online platforms and offline media.

5. Exploitation Activities

BIOFIN-EU will produce several KERs (commercial) that will be freely exploited during the lifespan of the project. This chapter will introduce the preliminary results identified during the proposal stage (KERs), and potential pathways for their exploitation as well as the procedure for identifying new potential KERs (and IPs) during project implementation. A set of clear measures to ensure sustainability and effective IPR management of BIOFIN-EU results will be developed by the Toolset for Multiplying Impact (D7.5) at M12, under Task 7.4 IPR Management and Sustainability Plan, which will consist of an IPR plan, a go-to-market strategy plan and a sustainability plan and will be updated as a second and third version at M24 and M36 respectively.

BIOFIN recognises that a sound exploitation plan will effectively:

- Ensure the **use, re-use** and extensive dissemination of knowledge created during the project.
- Highlight the added value of the project to promote further scientific development.
- Promote sustainable growth

5.1. BIOFIN-EU exploitation strategy and measures

A specific procedure has been set for the definition of the project's KERs, the identification of new KERs other than those already identified, their validation, characterization and development of the final exploitation plan of each KER from a specific partner, group of partners or external organisation. A complete exploitation strategy will be established by M03 as part of the DEC plan, designed to bring BIOFIN-EU results to all target groups and deliver sustainable outputs that extend beyond the project lifetime. The strategy will follow a multi-actor approach through 3 cycles:

Cycle 1: Investigate - Explore partner expectations and ambitions for future business development. BIOFIN-EU will base its initial strategy for management of Intellectual Property (section 5.3), by performing an IPR Scan for all partners. IP expectations information collection form and individual interview, resulting in an agreed-upon set of IPR measures.

This cycle involves the development of the "KERs Inventory & IPRs" online tool, which validates the existing knowledge and information about the project's Key Exploitable Results and possible IPRs that the partners have already identified.

In this tool the list of the identified KERs is provided where partners are asked to state the scope of exploitation, the KERs' target groups, the means of exploitation and to identify possible IPRs that derive from the exploitation of the identified project's results. For each partner there is a separate sheet with their organisation's acronym providing them with an individual space for information and updates. The tool has already been shared with the partners and is available for further update at any time on the project's SharePoint (**Annex IV**).

Through BIOFIN-EU's Key Impact Pathways (KIPs), the main aim of the exploitation plan is to ensure the optimal use of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) accompanied with their **Unique Value Proposition (UVP)** for both **commercial** and **non-commercial** use and therefore, to speed up their uptake by targeted stakeholders, ensuring wide use and maximum impact to the economy, society, science and technology.

At the time of writing, BIOFIN-EU has identified the following four Key Exploitable Results, available for use/reuse by partners and target group stakeholders. Table 8 presents each of the KERs, the partners that will contribute to their development, a description, the target groups, the scope (commercial, non-commercial) and means of exploitation as well as the unique value proposition. This brief statement clearly

explains the benefits, how it solves a particular challenge and how it is different and unique. As the project progresses, each of the KERs will be revisited and analysed in further detail.

Table 8: Key Exploitable Results Matrix (Marketability: C: Commercial, N: Non-commercial)

	Exploitation Goal	By whom	For whom
KER 1 N&C	BIOFIN Database: A data platform incorporating high quality Biodiversity and ES data from heterogenous and multiscale NBS sources. Free during the lifespan of the project and then commercial		
	<u>Academia:</u> Exploitation of the NBS/ES data for conducting new breakthrough research. <u>Financial Actors and Professionals:</u> Effective data platform facilitating internal, R&D activity and evaluation of 'external' third party NBS solutions	UL, NAT, QUB, IST, SERDA, UNIPD, ETI, ILSI	Research Organisations, Financial Actors
UVP	The Database will be enriched with both NBS-promotor and NBS-provider led trustworthy and accurate data.		
KER 2 N&C	BIOFIN Nature-Positive Business Model Builder: Innovative Business Models that will support the decision-making towards NBS lending/investments. Free during the lifespan of the project and then commercial.		
	Strengthen the position of NBS - Promoters/Providers based on principles of mutuality, facilitating the collaboration with various value chain actors and creating win-win situations. Unlock new business opportunities and enter new markets for service providers in real time.	IOB, ILSI	Financial Actors, NBS Providers
UVP	Tailor-made business models designed to match the specific needs (e.g. Risk Assessments, reduced transaction costs) of all stakeholders, developed as a system with a sectoral approach and validated in real life use cases through the 8 unique BIOFIN learning sites.		
KER 3 N&C	BIOFIN Data Analytics & Underwriting Engine: A user-friendly dashboard that allows discovery, purchase / use and contribution of ES/NBS raw data and analytics services running on the BIOFIN NBS Dashboard. Free during the lifespan of the project and then commercial		
	<u>Data owners</u> will use friendly services of the marketplace to publish information available in their own platforms (i.e, data providers) and monetize them. <u>Data consumers</u> (e.g. Corporations, Financial Institutions, Public enterprises, Policy makers & regulators) will be able to explore available tools and information empowering their decision support processes.	IOB, ILSI	Research Organisations, Financial Actors, NBS Providers, Professional Ecosystem, Policy Makers & Standardisation bodies
UVP	Effective and all-encompassing decision-making support tool, enhancing competitiveness and efficiency.		
KER 4 N&C	Skills and Knowledge Accelerators: The portfolio of training, business simulation and case studies, mentoring courses of the BIOFIN activities will be publicly available through open repositories and under a Creative Commons licence during the lifespan of the project. Free during the lifespan of the project and then commercial.		

Transfer of new knowledge and capacity, upscale the skills development for current professional bankers and investment managers as well as the next generation of business leaders.	IOB, SUL, ILSI	Professional Ecosystem
UVP Comprehensive training courses, business simulations and associated tools and models, providing a curriculum emerged through testing in real life settings.		

As the project progresses additional KERs might be identified by the partners. Towards this direction, constant communication with partners helps in identifying possible exploitable results, commercial or non-commercial.

Cycle 2: Co-create - Continuous mapping of current trends, market watch and analysis. BIOFIN-EU will proceed towards the validation of exploitation scenarios (commercial & non-commercial) and identify the best market fit following the pace of progress of each pillar to capture accumulated value fully.

The co-create step also involves the identification of possible additional exploitable results that may be developed during the project. Towards this direction, constant communication with partners will help in identifying possible exploitable results.

To this end, a certain procedure and steps have been designed and are presented in Figure 33 below:

Figure 33: Steps for the identification and inclusion of a new KER

When one or more partners identify a new KER, the partner has to inform the WP7 Leader (RAINNO) and the coordinator (UL) providing a detailed explanation of the exploitability potential of the identified result by making sure it aligns with the project exploitation plan. The partner has to provide all relevant information about this KER using the “KERs Inventory & IPRs” online tool uploaded on the project’s SharePoint (**Annex IV**), covering at least the following aspects:

- Description of the exploitable result
- Scope of exploitation (scientific, commercial, policy making, training, other)
- Target groups
- Means of exploitation
- IPR(s) linked to the KER, if relevant.

Once the form has been completed, it will be shared with the coordinator as the starting point for discussion. Each new KER will be presented at the General Assembly for the consortium to validate. This is particularly important to ensure that the partners who will exploit the result and the target groups are properly identified, particularly if joint exploitation is a factor. If there are no objections, the KER will be included in the list and a distinct strategy for its exploitation will be developed.

Cycle 3: Accelerate - Finalise agreements on results' exploitation through dedicated workshops. Define (non)commercial synergies with potential partners/collaborators. Release the final version of the Exploitation Plan.

This cycle refers to the assessment of the exploitation strategy for each KER. To efficiently determine involvement of project partners in each of the KERs the BFMULO Matrix (Table 9) will be implemented, in which the partners will state their exploitable intentions using the following list:

B = IPR's on background information, excluding foreground information, brought to the project from existing knowledge, owned or controlled by project partners in the same or related fields of the work carried out in the research project.

F = IPR's on foreground information, Information including all kinds of exploitable results generated by the project partners or 3rd parties working for them in the implementation of the research project. To have an F in an exploitable result it is necessary that a partner has a task(s) in the project related to that very result.

M = Making the products, manufacturing, and selling or directly implementing it through own facilities and skills.

U = Using the result, implemented with own knowledge to develop new ranges of products or newer processing. Furthermore, the direct or indirect utilisation of foreground in further research activities other than those covered by the project, or for developing, creating, and marketing a product or process, or for creating and providing a service.

L = Licensing the result, therefore earning from a negotiation towards third parties outside the Consortium.

O = Other, any other exploitation means (e.g.: consultancy, provide services, etc.).

Table 9: BFMULO Matrix

#	Short name	KER1	KER2	KER3	KER4
1	UL				
2	NATURALIS				
3	UGOT				
4	UM				
5	RAINNO				
6	SERDA				
7	UNIPD				
8	ETIFOR SRL				
9	IOB				

10	SULITEST				
11	ILSI				
12	QUB				
13	COFAC				

In later stages, a characterisation table will be provided to partners which will exploit the project's key results. Each result requires a unique exploitation approach based upon the type, whether it can be commercialised, and if **Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)** are required and who will exploit the result. The characterization table will be offered to partners to characterise exploitable results (Table 10).

This table aims also to collect information for the Sustainability Plan and the Go to market Strategy that will be developed by the end of the project. The information and feedback included in the characterization table will serve as the foundation of the final exploitation plan of the KERs.

Table 10: Characterization table for potential exploitable results

CHARACTERISATION OF EXPLOITABLE RESULTS	
MARKET 	Who will the customer be and what benefits will they receive?
	What is the anticipated time to market?
	What is the size of the market in M€ and relevant trends?
	What is the approximate price range of this result and price of licences?
	Who are the competitors?
	How will this result rank against competing products/services in terms of price and/or performance?
STEPS TOWARDS EXPLOITATION 	When is the expected date of achievement?
	What are the foreseen barriers to successful implementation?
	What are the costs incurred after the project and before exploitation?
	Which partners will be involved in results development?
IPR STATUS 	Have you protected or will you protect this result? How? When?

5.2. Exploitation Pathways

A distinct exploitation plan will be established for each result; however, broad pathways may be defined for commercial results. Examples are included below.

5.2.1. Commercial results

For commercial results the business model canvas and a market analysis will be used. The **business model canvas** (Figure 34) offers a single page visualisation of the path to commercialization and defines several key components including:

1. **Key partners** who will be responsible for the creation and exploitation of the result;
2. **Key activities** required by the value proposition;
3. **Key resources** needed including human, physical, intellectual, financial;
4. **Value proposition** describing:
 - (i) The value of the result
 - (ii) The problem that is being addressed
 - (iii) The specifics of the product/service being offered
 - (iv) Which customer needs are being met?
5. **Customer relationships** expected to be established, delivered, and maintained with end users, which ones already exist and at what associated costs;
6. **Distribution channels** that work best, are preferred by customers and are cost-efficient;
7. **Customer segments** the results are targeting, who are the most important customers;
8. **Cost structure**, including the most important costs, the most expensive resource, and activities and whether the outcome is cost-driven or value-driven;
9. **Revenue streams**, what values customers are willing to pay, what do they currently pay, what are the possible streams (e.g., product, subscription fee, usage fee).

Figure 34: Business Model Canvas for commercial results

5.2.2. Sustainability Plan

A sustainability plan as part of the Integrated Toolset (D7.5) will be created for the long-term exploitation of non-commercial results to ensure their use/reuse continues after the project is no longer funded by Horizon EU and will consider:

- Responsible partners;
- Resources required (including person hours, technology);
- The value of results and what needs to remain exploitable;
- Specific tasks/ activities required for the result to remain valuable;
- Partnerships or joint actions that could better support long term exploitation than only the partners themselves;
- Alternative funding sources;

5.2.3. Go-To-Market (GTM) Strategy

BIOFIN's GTM strategy and sustainability planning development follows a lean multi-actor approach - a combination of the lean start-up methodology that focuses on the development of Minimal Viable Products in short iterations and the multi-actor approach that stresses the active involvement of various stakeholders. RAIN will simultaneously monitor the project (tech & non-tech) outcomes that are beneficial for the BIOFIN consortium to design a strategy for the successful market uptake of innovative solutions. A complete exploitation strategy will be established on M12 as part of the Integrated Toolset (D7.5), designed to bring BIOFIN results to all target groups and will be updated and enhanced over the BIOFIN lifespan, aiming to deliver sustainable outputs that extend beyond the project duration. To this end, BIOFIN will recognise amongst others the NBS market as well as the competitive landscape; BIOFIN's ambition is to synchronise and align its project findings and tools with dominant financial institutions (e.g. S&P's Sustainable Platform 1). GTM strategy will provide a plausible path to commercialise BIOFIN innovations through the exploitation strategy described in section 5.1.

5.3. IPR Strategy

The BIOFIN-EU consortium aims to develop a comprehensive and feasible strategy for the IP generated throughout the lifespan of the project. BIOFIN-EU's IPR strategy aims to align the impact pathways of the project with its outcomes and impacts, thus enhancing its overall credibility and making it "fit for purpose". BIOFIN-EU's IP approach will give due thought to balance between open science publication results and plans to adequately protect IP for commercial exploitation.

All KERs are potentially subject to IPR management. Task 7.4 (IPR Management and Sustainability Plan) through its dedicated deliverables (D7.5-D7.7) at M12, M24 and M36 will incorporate BIOFIN-EU's IPR Management and Sustainability Plan which will provide a detailed plan for each result and outline concrete IPR measures to be taken by the partners. BIOFIN-EU will examine the protection of any result that could potentially be commercially or industrially exploited, and if possible, reasonable, and justified, protect them. BIOFIN-EU is expected to produce significant research results and technological innovations. Hence, a strategy that will handle all IP rights matters will be developed, creating an encouraging environment for further exploitation of the generated discoveries and knowledge. As such, BIOFIN-EU handles IPR Management on a three-level approach covering the whole lifecycle of the project:

1. **IPR at Proposal Phase:** The consortium has already identified the outputs that are subject to IP/ownership which are the: (i) BIOFIN Database; (ii) BIOFIN Nature-Positive Business Model Builder;

(iii) and BIOFIN Data Analytics & Underwriting Engine. Access rights for exploitation or further research were agreed upon before the signing of any contract and granted fair and reasonable conditions and/or royalty-free. These latest were licensed under a copyleft license (eg. GPLv3, AGPL), mandating the open distribution of the source code, ensuring freedom of use and knowledge sharing. Refraining from using identical or similar characteristics to an IPR, preliminary searches were performed using the internet (Google Patents, Patent Lens) and the tools provided by EUIPO (Espacenet, eSearch plus), EUIPN (TMview) and WIPO (Global Brand Database)

2. **During the project:** Newly generated knowledge and related IPRs, will be recorded, recognised and assessed through appropriate mechanisms and tools (e.g., disclosure forms), in order to identify all relevant IP and clarify ownership, screening and managing any new IP that arises. All actors involved in the project will be asked to sign Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDAs) and the consortium will ensure that no unauthorised third party will have access to such information, applying information security policies and standards. The consortium will publish project results on the project platform, publications and seminars, without charging IPR. All peer reviewed and technical publications will be deposited in the BIOFIN-EU website and in a centralised repository (Open Research Europe) as mandated by the HE "Open science policy".
3. **Post-project IPR strategy:** Systematic management of IP risks is the building block of post-project sustainability. To this end, RAINNO will offer services for the whole IPR lifecycle to BIOFIN-EU partners concerning appropriate protection of results, provided that protecting them is possible, reasonable and justified.
4. **IPR Confidentiality:** Information collected for BIOFIN-EU will be considered de facto confidential unless it is known as public. Access to participant information and data derived from that information will require authorization from the provider of this data. All participants at project activities will be asked to provide informed consent, and permission to use the data within the confines of the project. The consortium shall ensure that no unauthorised third party will have access to such information, applying information security policies and standards.

Identification of new IPRs project procedure as the project progresses additional IPRs might be identified by the partners. To this end, a certain procedure and steps have been designed and presented in Figure 35 below:

Figure 35: Newly identified IPRs procedure

The identification of new IPRs is closely related to the identification process of KERs described above. In that way, when a new IPR is identified, the partner follows the same procedure by informing the coordinator on the relative IPR that is linked to the KER as presented in **Annex IV**.

Following, the partners are asked to validate the new IPR. Comments and suggestions of the partners are recorded while possible objections are discussed and addressed. Finally, after the new IPR is validated, it is included in the project's IPR list.

6. Conclusions

D7.1 “Dissemination, exploitation, communication plan”, has provided an overview of the communication, dissemination and exploitation phases during the whole project lifetime. The intention of this document is to outline the initial DEC plan which will be implemented during the first period of the BIOFIN-EU project, as well as the tools that will be utilised in order to reach DEC’s KPIs and project’s audience.

More specifically, the document covers a wide range of key activities (as well as sets their timelines) to be conducted to meet the dissemination, communication, and exploitation targets. All partners will be actively involved in the communication and dissemination of BIOFIN-EU aiming to ensure the proper exploitation of the project’s outcomes and maximise the impact.

The Second Dissemination, exploitation, communication plan, due M12, will be an updated version of the DEC plan. It will evaluate the current plan to identify weaknesses and strengths of the applied activities and tools and establish objectives and concrete actions beyond M12 until the third iteration (M24). The third version (M24) will focus on the diffusion of the scientific and technological information generated during the project and emphasis will be placed on sparking interest in the BIOFIN-EU platform and broadening stakeholder engagement with the project activities and results.

Annex I: BIOFIN-EU Overview of the D&C reporting tool

Instructions

This spreadsheet is designed to report on dissemination and communication activities directly linked to the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) outlined in the Grant Agreement (GA). It includes specific targets for each partner and reporting period.

Sheet 1A provides the total KPI targets per reporting period and a short description of each KPI.

Sheet 1B provides the total KPI targets per partner.

Sheet 1C monitors the KPI status.

Sheets 1 - 14 are dedicated to each partner, containing two tables:

- Dissemination Activities (e.g. events, synergies, publications) & Communications Activities (e.g. social media, interviews)

Please use the drop down menu to select the "Month" of the activity (column A) and double click to add the "Activity Day" (column B)

Please use the drop down menu to select "KPI" (column C) including both Dissemination and Communication KPIs, then provide the "Title / Description", "Link", and "Proofing material" (columns E, F, G).

If you are reporting Dissemination activities, please add "Type of stakeholders reached" and "No. of stakeholders reached" (columns H, I). Please indicate if the activity should be considered a "Joint activity" (external to the consortium), and "If yes, please indicate with whom" (columns J, K).

- If you need to add more info, please use the "Notes" (column L)
- In case there is nothing to report in a month, please make sure to select "Nothing to report" from the drop down menu in the "KPI" (column C).
- If you are reporting an activity beyond the BIOFIN-EU KPIs, please state "Other" in the "KPI" category in column C.

For Communication activities, there is no need to add "Type of stakeholders reached", "No. of stakeholders reached, joint Action", and "If yes, with whom"

- The "Report Status" (column D) gives you information on the status of the reporting process. Please don't overwrite, it is autofilled!
- The "D/C" (column M) indicates if the activity reported in a Dissemination or a Communication activity. Please don't overwrite, it is autofilled!

KPI Distribution:

(Please don't add any data here, all table is autofilled based on the activities reported in the previous table)

- The overall target for each KPI per partner.
- The achieved KPIs in RP1 (MS-18).
- The current status for each KPI, which is autofilled based on your reporting in the previous table (I). Please don't overwrite!

Important notes

Please click on the link on "Proofing material uploaded (Photos, screenshots etc.)" (cell G1) to upload photos or other relevant material (e.g. agenda, presentations) from events that may be used for dissemination and communication purposes.

For enhanced visibility and credibility, it is highly recommended that all dissemination posts related to the project come from your organization's official social media account, rather than personal accounts. Additionally, please ensure to tag @BIOFIN-EU in your posts to increase engagement.

"Report Status" column:

- all info added
- basic info missing
- minor info missing

"Status" column:

- KPI achieved
- KPI on progress
- no progress has been done yet

Please ensure to include the exact date of the activity and any relevant links. Please focus on input/activities that relate directly to the KPIs.

Reporting Month	Activity Day	KPI	Type of Stakeholders reached	No. of Stakeholders reached	Joint Action	If yes, with whom	Status	D/C	Report Status
Jan 2023	Feb 21	D.1.1 Publications in peer-reviewed journals	None	0	No				
Mar 2023	Apr 01	D.2.3 Technical publications/articles	None	0	No				

Partner	Target	K-16	K-17	K-18	K-19	K-20	K-21	K-22	K-23	K-24	K-25	K-26	K-27	K-28	K-29	K-30	K-31	K-32	K-33	K-34	K-35	K-36	K-37	K-38	K-39	K-40	K-41	K-42	K-43	K-44	K-45	K-46	K-47	K-48	K-49	K-50		
1.1 Scientific Publications	12	4	3	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
1.2 Publications in scientific conferences	16	4	3	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
1.3 Publications in scientific conferences	20	4	3	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Instructions

1A - KPIs per RP

2A - Partner breakdown

3A - Monitoring

1. UL

2. NAT

3. UG

4. UM

5. . . .

Annex II: BIOFIN-EU Brand Book

BIOFIN-EU

Flip the script:
Unlock finance
to protect & restore
biodiversity

Brand Guidelines

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Project Logo |

BIOFIN-EU

Logo Variations |

BIOFIN-EU

Colour scheme - Palette |

Primary		Secondary	
 #180 01-03 B111	WEB #A8B6F0	 #180 01-10 B140	WEB #E8A48C
 #120 02-15 086	WEB #F8D556	 #120 02-30 B111	WEB #F78E6F
 #17 02-19 B131	WEB #111787	 #120 02-64 B110	WEB #F8A4A4
 #194 01-06 B138	WEB #C2C4C6	 #150 02-10 B154	WEB #90808A
 #35 04-03 Y55 K5	PANTONE 7504 C	 #30 03-03 Y45 K0	PANTONE 7535 C
 #70 04-05 Y85 K0	PANTONE 7737 C	 #35 04-03 Y70 K0	PANTONE 5177 C
 #100 03-00 Y40 K10	PANTONE 7733 C	 #35 04-03 Y90 K5	PANTONE 5493 C
 #0 04-00 Y0 K30	PANTONE 4217 C	 #0 04-00 Y0 K50	PANTONE Cool Gray 7 C

BIOFIN-EU

Typography |

Aa

Headline 1
Zwo Pro Extra Bold

Headline 2
Zwo Pro Bold

Body Text 1
Zwo Pro Regular

Body Text 2
Zwo Pro Light

BIOFIN-EU

Applications |

BIOFIN-EU

Annex III: BIOFIN-EU Deliverable Template

BIOFIN-EU

PROTECTING AND RESTORING BIODIVERSITY USING MAINSTREAM FINANCE

DX.X: [Deliverable Title]

Lead Author: [Author Name and Surname (Partner)]

DX.X: Deliverable Title

Grant Agreement No.	101135476
Project Acronym	BIOFIN-EU
Project Title	Protecting and Restoring Biodiversity using Mainstream Finance
Type of action	HORIZON-ERA
Horizon Europe Call Topic	HORIZON-CL4-2021-BIODIV-01-9
Start - ending date	1 January 2024 - 31 December 2026
Project Website	biofin-project.eu
Work Package	WP: Title of the WP
WP Lead Beneficiary	Partner's full name (Short name)
Deliverable Title(s)	Title of the Task
Deliverable type / Classification level	R - Report; CSC: Webinars, press & media actions, videos, etc.; OTHER: Software, etc.; F EU: Public; SEN: Sensative; CI: Classified
Due Date of Deliverable	DD Month 20YY
Actual Submission Date	DD Month 20YY
Responsible Author	[Author Name and Surname (Partner)]
Contributors	[Contributor's Name and Surname (Partner)]
Reviewer(s)	[Reviewer's Name and Surname (Partner)]

Document History

Date	Version	Changes	Contributor(s)
DD/MM/YYYY	VL1	[Description of changes]	[Contributor's Name and Surname (Partner)]
DD/MM/YYYY	VLX	[Description of changes]	[Contributor's Name and Surname (Partner)]

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DX.X: Deliverable Title

BIOFIN-EU Consortium			
#	Organisation name	Short name	Country
1	UNIVERSITY OF LIMERICK	UL	IE
2	STICHTING NATURALIS BIODIVERSITY CENTER	NATURALIS	NL
3	SCHLESISCHES UNIVERSITÄT	UGUT	DE
4	UNIVERSITEIT MAASTRICHT	UM	NL
5	RAINNO (DIOITHI KEFALAIOUCHIKI ETAFERIA)	RAINNO	EL
6	SARAJEVSKA REGIONALNA RAZVOJNA AGENCIJA SERDA ODO SARAJEVO	SERDA	BA
7	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI PADOVA	UNPD	IT
8	ETFOR SRL	ETFOR SRL	IT
9	THE INSTITUTE OF BANKERS IN IRELAND	IOB	IE
10	SUSTAINABILITY LITERACY TEST	SALITEST	FR
11	INTERNATIONAL LIFE SCIENCES INSTITUTE EUROPEAN BRANCH AIGAL	ILSI	BE
12	THE QUEEN'S UNIVERSITY OF BELFAST	QUB	UK
13	COFAC COOPERATIVA DE FORMAGAO E ANIMAGAO CULTURAL CRL	COFAC	PT

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DX.X: Deliverable Title

Executive Summary

Goal of the executive summary section is to provide a short summary for the deliverable and inform the reader on:

- The subject of the deliverable
- Summary of the work carried out
- The main conclusion(s)
- The purpose of the deliverable

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DX.X: Deliverable Title

Table of Contents

1. Chapter 1	2
1.1. Section 1.1	2
1.1.1. Subsection 1.1.1	2
1.1.2. Subsection 1.1.2	2
2. Chapter 2	3
3. Chapter 3	4
4. Conclusion	5
5. References	7
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List of Figures

Figure 1 Example

List of Tables

Table 1 Example

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation #1	Acronym #1

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DX.X: Deliverable Title

1. Chapter 1

Paragraph Text

1.1. Section 1.1

1.1.1. Subsection 1.1.1.

1.1.1.1. Subsection 1.1.1.1.

1.1.1.1.1. Subsection 1.1.1.1.1.

Table 1 Example

Title	Title	Title

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2. Chapter 2

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3. Chapter 3

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DX.X: Deliverable Title

4. Conclusion

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<p>DX.X. Deliverable Title</p> <p>biofin-project.eu</p> <p>biofin-project.eu</p> <p>Example of landscape layout (including custom header and footer)</p> <p>Paragraph Text text text</p> <p>Paragraph Text text text</p> <p>*Note: When using this layout, make sure that the section breaks remain in the correct place. Use CTRL+* to switch paragraph marks and make sure there is a "section break" at the end of this page and as the last element on the previous page.</p> <p>Also make sure that the footers of sections following a page in landscape format are aligned from the previous section, if necessary.</p> <p>biofin-project.eu Page 6</p>	<p>DX.X. Deliverable Title</p> <p>biofin-project.eu</p> <p>5. References</p> <p>biofin-project.eu Page 7</p> <p>Funded by the European Union</p>	<p>DX.X. Deliverable Title</p> <p>biofin-project.eu</p> <p>Annex I</p> <p>biofin-project.eu Page 8</p> <p>Funded by the European Union</p>
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Annex IV: Identification of new KERs & IPR process

KERs (Key Exploitable Results)		Scope of exploitation		Target groups [to whom]	Means of exploitation	Linked IPRs to the KERs	
<i>Please validate the already identified KERs (1-3) and add any other exploitable results if relevant</i>		<i>Please validate (for further explanation of the scope, please see note)</i>		<i>Please validate (see note for the list of target groups)</i>	<i>Please indicate the means of exploitation, where relevant</i>	<i>Please indicate what might be the possible IPRs, where relevant</i>	
		<i>If "other", please identify</i>	<i>Other</i>			<i>If "other", please identify</i>	<i>Other</i>
1	BIOFIN Database	Commercial		Research Organisations, Financial Actors	"This was initially identified as an exploitable result for your organisation. Could you please clarify how you envision its exploitation."		
2	BIOFIN Nature-Positive Business Model Builder	Commercial		Financial Actors, NBS Providers	<i>If relevant, please indicate the means of exploitation</i>		
3	BIOFIN Data Analytics & Underwriting Engine	Commercial		Research Organisations, Financial Actors, NBS Providers, Professional Ecosystem, Policy Makers & Standardisation bodies	<i>If relevant, please indicate the means of exploitation</i>		
4	Skills and Knowledge Accelerators	Commercial		Professional Ecosystem	<i>If relevant, please indicate the means of exploitation</i>		
5	Other individual or joint exploitable result (if any)						

Identified Background

Please validate the background described in the Consortium Agreement or revise accordingly

This is the description in the Consortium Agreement for your organisation: